

Sanja Marjanović, LL.D.,*
Associate Professor,
Faculty of Law University of Niš,

UDK: 341.24:[341.9:347.61/.64(497.11)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14570082

Sanja Đorđević Aleksovski, LL.D.,**
Assistant Professor,
Faculty of Law University of Niš,
Republic of Serbia

HCCH CONVENTIONS AND THE BILATERAL TREATIES IN THE SERBIAN PRIVATE INTERNATIONAL LAW (FAMILY RELATIONS) - EVERYTHING EVERYWHERE ALL AT ONCE?***

Abstract: *Currently, thirteen Hague conventions on Private International Law bind the Republic of Serbia. Concurrently, numerous bilateral treaties which are in force in the Republic of Serbia regulate various Private International Law matters, completely or partially corresponding to the relevant HCCH conventions. Most of these bilateral treaties stem from the period of former Yugoslavia, when they were tailored to fit the frequent PIL relations mostly with the states which later became EU Member States. On the other hand, the conflict clauses in the relevant Hague Conventions adopted in the family law matters are often neutral in respect of their priority over other corresponding international treaties binding the same Contracting States. Some of these clauses merge their neutrality with the possibility to declare the primacy of the specific Hague convention. Yet, when the other state is an EU Member State, this clause does not seem to leave an escape, which generates further perplexity. Consequently, the international treaties hierarchy labyrinth expands, imposing the systemic integration as part of the law of treaties and International Public Law. However, the International Public Law's systemic integration patchwork does not match up with the Serbian bilateral PIL treaties when they amalgamate with the HCCH conven-*

* sanja@prafak.ni.ac.rs, ORCID 0000-0001-7560-8254

** sanjadj@prafak.ni.ac.rs, ORCID: 0000-0003-2827-8728

*** The paper is the result of research on the project "Responsibility in legal and social context", financed by the Faculty of Law of the University of Niš, in the period 2021-2025.

*tions. In effect, it prevents the rational and efficient outcome, especially in cross-border family matters, where the Serbian bilateral treaties are to be systematically applied with the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention, the 2007 Hague Maintenance Protocol or the 2007 Hague Child Support Convention. In this regard, the authors of this paper strive to disentangle the IPL and PIL's nodus regarding the relevant Serbian bilateral PIL treaties and the corresponding Hague conventions in family law matters. Thus, the paper addresses the following dilemmas: can States tacitly manifest their intention to supersede the prior treaty, especially when the joint declaration on the posterior convention's priority cannot be anticipated due to the legal or factual obstacles; are the bilateral treaties always in compliance with the *lex specialis* rule or may they reverse it in certain cases?*

Keywords: *compatibility clauses, gentleman's clause, lex specialis, systemic integration, HCCH conventions, bilateral PIL treaties, cross-border family relations.*

1. Introduction

In terms of the Serbian Private International Law, the entry into force of the 2007 Hague Maintenance Obligation Protocol in 2013,¹ and the 1993 Hague Inter-country Adoption Convention² in 2014, followed by the Hague Children Protection Convention³ in 2016, and most lately, by the 2007 Hague Child Support Convention in 2021,⁴ raised the specific issue of their hierarchy (and relation with) the bilateral PIL treaties binding Serbia in the corresponding matters.

Before addressing the core of the problem, it is necessary to point out several facts, which are pivotal for further discussion. Hence, we have to return to the time of former Yugoslavia. The HCCH conventions in force in Serbia stem from two periods. The first one began in 1930 when the King-

¹ Protocol on the Law Applicable to Maintenance Obligations, *Official Gazette of the RS - International Agreements*, 1/2013,

² Convention on Protection of Children and Co-operation in Respect of Inter-country Adoption, *Official Gazette of RS - International Agreements*, 12/2013.

³ Convention on Jurisdiction, Applicable Law, Recognition, Enforcement and Co-operation in respect of Parental Responsibility and Measures for the Protection of Children, *Official Gazette of RS - International Treaties*, 20/2015.

⁴ Convention on the International Recovery of Child Support and Other Forms of Family Maintenance, *Official Gazette of RS - International Agreements*, 4/2020.

dom of Yugoslavia ratified the first Hague Convention (1905 Convention relative à la procédure civile⁵) as well as several bilateral PIL treaties (with the Great Britain,⁶ the USA,⁷ Switzerland,⁸ and the Netherlands⁹). This period persisted until the end of the Second World War. Afterwards, two differently named states were established subsequently, following relevant constitutional changes (FPRY and SFRY), known in plain English, as Yugoslavia. This period lasted further on until the dissolution of the SFRY in the 1990s. In this period, the former Yugoslavia ratified the following HCCH conventions: the 1954 Civil Procedure Convention,¹⁰ the 1961 *Apostille* Convention,¹¹ the 1961 Form of Wills Convention,¹² the 1971 Traffic Accidents Convention,¹³ the 1973 Products Liability Convention,¹⁴ the 1980 Access to Justice Convention,¹⁵ and the 1980 Child Abduction Convention,¹⁶ as the last one, ratified in 1991.

Meanwhile, former Yugoslavia entered into numerous bilateral PIL treaties to which we refer as the so called “old” bilateral PIL treaties (e.g. with

⁵ *Official Gazette of the Kingdom of Yugoslavia*, 100/1930.

⁶ Agreement on trade and navigation between the Kingdom of Serbs, Croats and Slovenians (SCS) and the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Ireland, *Official Gazette*, 46/1928. Convention between the Kingdom of Yugoslavia and Great Britain on the arrangement of mutual assistance in conducting proceedings in civil and commercial matters pending or which may be pending before the respective judicial authorities, *Official Gazette*, 116/1937.

⁷ Trade agreement between Serbia and the United States of America, *Serbian Official Gazette*, 268/1882.

⁸ Convention on settlement and consular relations between Serbia and Switzerland, *Official Gazette*, 83/1888.

⁹ Agreement on trade and navigation between the Kingdom of Yugoslavia and the Kingdom of the Netherlands, *Official Gazette of the Kingdom of Yugoslavia*, 85-XXXVII/32.

¹⁰ Convention on Civil Procedure, *Official Gazette of the FPRY – International Treaties and other Agreements*, 6/1962.

¹¹ Convention on Abolishing the Requirement of Legalisation for Foreign Public Documents, *Official Gazette of the FPRY – International Treaties and other Agreements*, 10/1962.

¹² Convention on the Conflicts of Laws Relating to the Form of Testamentary Dispositions, *Official Gazette of the FPRY – supplement*, 11/1962.

¹³ Convention on the Law Applicable to Traffic Accidents, *Official Gazette of the SFRY – supplement* 26/1976.

¹⁴ Convention on the Law Applicable to Products Liability, *Official Gazette of the SFRY – International Agreements*, 8/1977.

¹⁵ Convention on International Access to Justice, *Official Gazette of the SFRY – International Treaties* 4/1988.

¹⁶ Convention on the Civil Aspects of International Child Abduction, *Official Gazette of the SFRY – International Treaties*, 7/1991.

the Kingdom of Greece, Romania,¹⁷ Czechoslovakia,¹⁸ Poland,¹⁹ Hungary,²⁰ Austria, Belgium, France, Bulgaria,²¹ Cyprus,²² Italy, the USSR,²³ Algeria,²⁴ Iraq,²⁵ Mongolia,²⁶ Iran,²⁷ Japan,²⁸ Norway,²⁹ etc).³⁰ Multiple bilateral treaties regulating different Private International Law issues had been concluded with some of these States, which later became the EU Member States: two

¹⁷ Agreement on Legal Assistance between the FPR Yugoslavia and the Romanian People's Republic (1960) - (Official Gazette of the FPRY - Supplement International Treaties 8 /1961)

¹⁸ Agreement on the Regulation of Legal Relations in Civil, Family and Criminal Matters between the SFR Yugoslavia and Czechoslovakia SR (1964) - (Official Gazette of the SFRY - Supplement International Treaties 13 / 1964)

¹⁹ Agreement on Legal Relations in Civil and Criminal Matters between the FPR Yugoslavia and PR Poland (1960) - (Official Gazette of the FPRY - Supplement International Treaties 5 /1963)

²⁰ Agreement on Mutual Legal Relations between the SFR Yugoslavia and the People's Republic of Hungary (1968), amended (1986) - (Official Gazette of the SFRY – Supplement International Treaties 3 /1968; with amendments – Official Gazette of the SFRY – Supplement International Treaties 1 / 1987)

²¹ Agreement on Mutual Legal Assistance between the FPR Yugoslavia and the People's Republic of Bulgaria (1956), Official Gazette of the SFRY – Supplement International Treaties 1/1957.

²² Agreement on Legal Assistance between the SFRY Yugoslavia and the Republic of Cyprus (1984), Official Gazette of the SFRY – Supplement International Treaties 2/1986).

²³ Agreement on Legal Assistance in Civil, Family and Criminal Matters between the FPR Yugoslavia and DPR Algeria (1982), Official Gazette of the FPRY, Supplement International Treaties 2/1981.

²⁴ Agreement on Legal Assistance between the SFRY Yugoslavia and the Republic of Cyprus (1984), Official Gazette of the SFRY – Supplement International Treaties 2/1986.

²⁵ Agreement on legal and judicial cooperation between SFRY and the Republic of Iraq (1986), Official Gazette of the SFRY – Supplement International Treaties 1/1987.

²⁶ Agreement on Legal Assistance in Civil, Family and Criminal Matters between the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia and the Mongolian People's Republic (1981), *Official Gazette of the SFRY - Supplement International Treaties*, 7/1982.

²⁷ Agreement between Yugoslavia and Iran on Mutual Exemption from *Cautio iudicatum solvi*, *Official Gazette of the FPRY - Supplement International Treaties*, 2/1957.

²⁸ Agreement on trade and navigation between FPR Yugoslavia and Japan, *Official Gazette of the FPRY - Supplement*, 7/1959.

²⁹ Agreement on reciprocal recognition of the diplomatic-consular form of marriage between Yugoslavia and Norway, *Official Gazette of the FPRY - International Treaties and other agreements*, 6/1958.

³⁰ The full list of all bilateral PIL treaties binding Serbia, with their original texts, is available at the official web site of the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Serbia, <https://www.mpravde.gov.rs/sr/tekst/25261/bilateralni-sporazumi-u-gradjanskim-stvarima-.php>.

of them with Greece (on international judicial assistance;³¹ and recognition and enforcement³²); three with Austria (on legal assistance,³³ recognition and enforcement of the maintenance decisions,³⁴ and recognition and enforcement of the decision of chosen courts³⁵); four with France (on extract of the civil status registries and legalization;³⁶ recognition and enforcement;³⁷ conflict of laws in family matters;³⁸ and the treaty on the simplified application of the 1954 Hague Convention³⁹); three with Belgium (on legal assistance,⁴⁰ recognition and enforcement of maintenance decisions,⁴¹ extract of civil registries and legalization of public documents⁴²); three with Italy (on legal and

³¹The Convention on Mutual Legal Relations between the FPR Yugoslavia and the Kingdom of Greece (1959), Official Gazette of the FPRY - Supplement International Treaties 7/1960.

³²Agreement on Mutual Recognition and Enforcement of Court Decisions between the SFR Yugoslavia and the Kingdom of Greece, Official Gazette of the SFRY, Supplement International Treaties 6/1960.

³³The Convention on Mutual Legal Relations between the FPR Yugoslavia and the Republic of Austria (1954), Official Gazette of the FPRY - Supplement International Treaties 8/1955.

³⁴Agreement on mutual recognition and enforcement of decisions on maintenance between FPR Yugoslavia and the Republic of Austria (1961), Official Gazette of the SFRY, 2/1963.

³⁵Agreement on mutual recognition and enforcement of decisions of chosen courts and settlements concluded before the chosen courts in commercial matters between the FPR Yugoslavia and the Republic of Austria (1960), Official Gazette of the SFRY, 5/1961.

³⁶Convention on Issuing Documents on Personal Status and on Exemption from Legalization between SFR Yugoslavia and the Republic of France, Official Gazette of the SFRY - International treaties and other agreements, 3/1971.

³⁷Convention on the recognition and enforcement of court decisions in civil and commercial matters between the SFR Yugoslavia and the Republic of France (1971), Official Gazette of the SFRY - Supplement, 7/1972.

³⁸Convention on Jurisdiction and the Applicable Law in the Matters of Personal and Family Law between the SFR Yugoslavia and the Republic of France (1971) - (Official Gazette of the SFRY - Supplement International Treaties 55/1972.

³⁹Agreement on Facilitating the Application of the Hague Convention on Civil Procedure of March 1, 1954 between the SFR Yugoslavia and the Republic of France, Official Gazette of the SFRY - Supplement International Treaties and other agreements, 21/1971.

⁴⁰Agreement on legal assistance in civil and commercial matters between the SFR Yugoslavia and the Kingdom of Belgium, Official Gazette of the SFRY - Supplement International Treaties and other agreements, 7/1974.

⁴¹Convention on the recognition and enforcement of court decisions on maintenance between the SFR Yugoslavia and the Kingdom of Belgium, Official Gazette of the SFRY - Supplement International Treaties and other agreements, 45/1976.

⁴²Convention on Issuing Extracts from Registers and Exemption from Legalization between the SFR Yugoslavia and the Kingdom of Belgium, Official Gazette of the SFRY, 55/1972.

judicial protection of the citizens,⁴³ legal assistance,⁴⁴ trade and navigation⁴⁵). Except from treaties with Algeria, Cyprus and Iraq, all other bilateral PIL treaties in this period were concluded while Yugoslavia still did not have a separate statutory act on Private International Law as a *lex generalis*. The PIL Act was enacted in 1982, and came into force on January 1st 1983.⁴⁶ This piece of legislation still applies, but only in Serbia and Bosnia and Herzegovina.

The second period of the HCCH conventions ratifications began during the existence of FRY. In this period, a treaty was concluded with Croatia.⁴⁷ Following the dissolution of the FRY and, afterwards, the dissolution of Serbia and Montenegro Union (2006), the 1970 Taking of Evidence Convention⁴⁸ and 1965 Service Convention⁴⁹ were ratified in 2010. This period still lasts and it has so far resulted in the ratifications of the earlier mentioned 1993 Adoption Convention, the 2007 Hague Protocol, the 1996 Children Protection Convention and the 2007 Child Support Convention. At the same time, Serbia has entered into bilateral PIL treaties primarily with the neighbouring States - Bosnia and Herzegovina,⁵⁰ Slovenia,⁵¹ North Macedonia,⁵² Montenegro,⁵³ but

⁴³ Convention between the Kingdom of the SCS and Italy on the legal and judicial protection of the respective citizens, Official Gazette of the Kingdom of Yugoslavia, 42/1931, but its provisions in civil matters were replaced by the Agreement cited in the next ft.

⁴⁴ Convention on mutual legal assistance in civil and administrative matters between the FPR of Yugoslavia and the Italian Republic, Official Gazette of the SFRY - International treaties and other agreements, 7/1974.

⁴⁵ Convention on trade and navigation between the FNR of Yugoslavia and the Italian Republic, Official Gazette - Supplement, 14/1956.

⁴⁶ Act on Resolving Conflict of Laws with the Regulations of other Countries, *Official Gazette of the SFRY*, 43/82 and 72/82 - corr., *Official Gazette of the FRY*, 46/96 and *Official Gazette of the of the RS*, 46/2006.

⁴⁷ Agreement between the FR Yugoslavia and the Republic of Croatia on legal assistance in civil and criminal matters (1997), Official Gazette of the FRY - International treaties, 1/1998.

⁴⁸ Convention on Taking of Evidence Abroad in Civil and Commercial matters, *Official Gazette of the RS - International Treaties* 1/2010 and 13/2013.

⁴⁹ Convention on the Service Abroad of Judicial and Extrajudicial Documents in Civil or Commercial Matters, *Official Gazette of the RS - International Agreements* 1/2010 and 13/2013.

⁵⁰ Agreement between the Republic of Serbia and Bosnia and Herzegovina on Amendments to the Agreement on Legal Assistance in Civil and Criminal Matters (2005), Official Gazette of the Serbia and Montenegro - International treaties, 6/2005, as amended (2010), Official Gazette of the RS - International Treaties, 13/2010.

⁵¹ Agreement between the Republic of Serbia and the Republic of Slovenia on legal assistance in civil and criminal matters (2011), Official Gazette of the RS - International Treaties, 9/2011.

⁵² Agreement between the Republic of Serbia and the Republic of Macedonia on legal assistance in civil and criminal matters (2012), Official Gazette of the RS - International Treaties, 5/2012.

⁵³ Agreement between the Republic of Serbia and Montenegro on legal assistance in civil

also with Belorussia,⁵⁴ Turkey,⁵⁵ and the most lately - with the UAE.⁵⁶ In this paper, we will focus on those “old” bilateral PIL treaties binding for Serbia and certain EU Member States in family relations since all of the EU States apply the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention, the 2007 Hague Maintenance Protocol and the 2007 Hague Child Support Convention.⁵⁷ Although those “old” bilateral PIL treaties under the title “legal assistance” may associate only to the legal assistance *stricto sensu*, the most of the “old” bilateral PIL treaties of this type regulate also some of the rules on cross-border family relations and succession, sometimes followed by the provisions on general regime of recognition and enforcement. While regulating conflict of laws, international jurisdiction and/or recognition and enforcement, these bilateral treaties are, to the certain extent, intertwining especially with the 2007 Hague Maintenance Protocol and the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention, as well as with the 2007 Hague Child Support Convention but to a lesser extent due to the express *lex favorabilis* rule.

2. Types of the provisions on compatibility clauses envisaged in the relevant HCCH conventions and one hypothetical case

Before we dive into the troubled waters of the Private International Law and International Public Law melting point, one should bear in mind that these bilateral PIL treaties bind Serbia and the relevant EU Member State since the socialist period of the former Yugoslavia. In order to analyze the law of the treaties rules as the intersection of PIL and IPL regarding the hierarchy of successive international treaties, it is necessary to take a look on the types of the provisions on the hierarchy between the relevant HCCH conventions and other international treaties. While regulating the conflict-of-laws alone (the 2007 Hague Maintenance Protocol), or in conjunction with direct international jurisdiction and/or recognition and enforcement (the

and criminal matters (2009), Official Gazette of the RS - International Treaties, 1/2010.

⁵⁴ Agreement between the Republic of Serbia and the Republic of Belarus on legal assistance in civil and criminal matters (2013), Official Gazette of the RS - International Treaties, 13/2013.

⁵⁵ Agreement between the Republic of Serbia and the Republic of Turkey on mutual legal assistance in civil and commercial matters (2015), Official Gazette of the RS - International Treaties, 15/2015.

⁵⁶ Agreement on legal and judicial cooperation in civil and commercial matters between the Republic of Serbia and the United Arab Emirates (2023), Official Gazette of the RS - International Treaties, 7/2022.

⁵⁷ The full list of all bilateral PIL treaties binding Serbia is available at the official web site of the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Serbia, <https://www.mpravde.gov.rs/sr/tekst/25261/bilateralni-sporazumi-u-gradjanskim-stvarima-iph>.

2007 Hague Child Support Convention, or the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention), all three of the relevant HCCH conventions have introduced express provisions on their relations to the other treaties. These provisions are usually referred to as the conflict clauses⁵⁸ or compatibility clauses.⁵⁹ With exception of the 2007 Hague Child Support Convention, the 2007 Hague Maintenance Protocol and the 1996 Children Protection Convention share an identical idea on this issue. The only difference is whether these two HCCH convention regulate their hierarchical relation regarding prior or subsequent successive treaty.

According to the 1969 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (VCLT), the question of conflicts between earlier and later treaties is covered by article 30, having in mind different scenarios - where there are identical parties to the treaties, and the other of non-identical parties. Having in mind the subject matter of this paper, only the first scenario is relevant. In international law, the interplay between successive treaties concerning the same subject matter hinges on the principles of *lex posterior derogat priori* (later law prevails over earlier law) and *lex specialis derogat legi generali* (special law prevails over general law). When successive treaties involve the same parties, the principle of *lex posterior* generally governs, dictating that the later treaty takes precedence.⁶⁰ However, if the earlier treaty exhibits a special character in relation to the later one, the *lex specialis* principle prevails, granting priority to the more specific treaty.

This interplay is further nuanced by Article 59 of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (VCLT), which addresses the termination of treaties. According to Article 59, when the parties to an earlier treaty are also parties to a later treaty on the same subject matter, the earlier treaty survives

⁵⁸The term *conflict clauses* is used in the Fragmentation Report, Study Group of the International Law Commission, finalized by Mr. Martti Koskenniemi. Study Group of the International Law Commission, *Fragmentation of International Law: difficulties arising from the diversification and expansion of International Law, Document A/CN.4/L.682 and Add.1*, finalized by Mr. Martti Koskenniemi, 13 April 2006, pp. 268-271, available at: https://legal.un.org/ilc/documentation/english/a_cn4_l682.pdf (further on: Fragmentation Report);

⁵⁹The term *compatibility clauses* i used e.g. in Blanca Noodt Taquela, M., *Applying the Most Favourable Treaty or Domestic Rules to Facilitate Private International Law Co-Operation*, Collected Courses of the Hague Academy of International Law, Vol. 377, Brill|Nijhoff, 2015, pp. 208-248; but also Lagarde, P., *Explanatory report on the 1996 HCCH Child Protection Convention, Proceedings of the Eighteenth Session (1996), tome II, Protection of children*. Hague: HCCH, 1996, 601.

⁶⁰Fragmentation Report, paras 223-323; Murphy, S. D., *Deconstructing Fragmentation: Koskenniemi's 2006 ILC Project*, Temple International & Comparative Law Journal, Vol. 27, Issue 2, 2013, p. 295.

only if its provisions are compatible with those of the later treaty. This provision implies a presumption that when states conclude a subsequent treaty incompatible with an earlier one, they intend to terminate or modify the earlier treaty unless evidence suggests otherwise. The application of these principles, however, is not mechanical and requires careful consideration of the context, including: party intent,⁶¹ treaty interpretation⁶² and the nature of the treaties.⁶³

Ultimately, resolving potential conflicts between successive treaties necessitates a nuanced approach that considers the specific circumstances of each case and aims to balance the principles of *lex posterior* and *lex specialis* with the overarching goal of maintaining coherence and stability within the international legal system.

Hence, when two states have concluded two treaties on the same subject matter but have not addressed their mutual relationship, the standard practice is to interpret the treaties as compatible with each other,⁶⁴ reflecting the principle of harmonization,⁶⁵ a cornerstone of systemic integration in international law. The principle of harmonization reflects a presumption that states, acting in good faith, do not intend to create conflicting legal obligations. Therefore, unless a clear intention to derogate from an earlier treaty is evident, interpreters strive to find an interpretation that upholds the validity and effectiveness of both treaties. This approach promotes stability and predictability in international law by ensuring that treaty obligations are interpreted in a way that minimizes conflict and maximizes their mutual compatibility.

⁶¹ Fragmentation Report, para. 230.

⁶² Murphy, S. D., op. cit., p. 296; Fragmentation Report, para. 58, 229.

⁶³ Fragmentation Report, paras 61, 65, 79, 223.

⁶⁴ Czaplinski, W., Danilenko, G., Conflicts of norms in international law, Netherlands Yearbook of International Law, vol. XXI, 1990, p. 13; Aust, A., Modern Treaty Law and Practice, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2000, p. 174; Pauwelyn, J., Conflict of Norms in Public International Law: How WTO Law Relates to Other Rules of International Law, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2003, pp. 240-244; Jenks, C. W., The conflict of law-making treaties, British Yearbook of International Law, Vol. 30, 1953, pp. 427-429.

⁶⁵ Harmonization seeks to avoid conflict and promote coherence within the international legal system by interpreting seemingly conflicting norms in a way that renders them compatible. A common method for achieving harmonization is to examine party intent. This involves analyzing the treaty texts to discern the states' objectives and understanding of their obligations. By considering various interpretations of the treaty language, legal practitioners and scholars can determine whether a reading exists that allows both treaties to operate concurrently without contradiction. This process often requires considering the broader context of the treaties, including their purpose, subsequent practice, and relevant rules of international law, as highlighted by Article 31 of the VCLT.

The 2007 Hague Maintenance Protocol, as the first ratified HCCH convention by Serbia as an independent state, envisages that “this Protocol does not affect any other international instrument to which Contracting States are or become Parties, and which contains provisions on matters governed by the Protocol, unless a contrary declaration is made by the States Parties to such instrument”.⁶⁶ This provision regulates the relation between the 2007 Maintenance Protocol with both prior and subsequent international successive treaty by the *neutral* clause. This type of compatibility clause points to the “clauses which are not expressly oriented in the direction of maximum effectiveness”,⁶⁷ as Professor Tequela refers to them in her lecture given at the Hague Academy. However, in this paper we plead for the use of the term *gentleman’s clause*, in order to succinctly and concisely illustrate the notion of this type of compatibility clauses as being neutral. The 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention regulates its relations with prior and subsequent international successive treaties introducing the same *gentleman’s clause*.⁶⁸ On the other hand, the 2007 Hague Child Support Convention envisages the most effective rule (*lex favorabilis*) stating that the other treaty has priority under certain conditions which makes the specific treaty most favourable in the same matter.⁶⁹

However, the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention and the 2007 Hague Maintenance Protocol provide the clause authorising the States who are contracting parties of the relevant HCCH convention (the 2007 Hague Maintenance Protocol⁷⁰ or the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention⁷¹) and concurrent international treaty to negotiate on the priority of the HCCH convention in question, and to give express declaration on its priority. However, if these declarations have not been given, the *gentleman’s clause* is set in stone. The *gentleman’s clause* does not give *a priori* primacy to the anterior international successive treaty. Instead, the Contracting States are authorised to interpret the treaties in force between them as being coordinated (or not contrary to one another).⁷² The aim of these clauses is to prevent the treaty from being interpreted in the sense that it would supersede previous treaties.⁷³ This type of compatibility clause leaves the door open for

⁶⁶ Article 19 (1) of the 2007 Hague Maintenance Protocol.

⁶⁷ Blanca Noodt Taquela, M. (2015), 218-227.

⁶⁸ Article 52 of the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention.

⁶⁹ Article 52 of the 2007 Hague Child Support Convention.

⁷⁰ Article 19 (1) of the 2007 Hague Maintenance Protocol.

⁷¹ Article 52 (1) of the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention.

⁷² Blanca Noodt Taquela, M. (2015), 223.

⁷³ *Ibid*, 219.

the systemic integration approach when dealing with the issue of hierarchy of international treaties. This approach stems from IPL, where it is firmly incorporated, as *the sedes materiae rule* of its Law of Treaties.

Systemic integration is a legal principle that promotes the interpretation of international law as a unified and coherent system, emphasizing the interconnectedness of the international legal system. It proposes that different parts of international law, such as treaties, customary law and general principles of law, as well as different sub-regimes in international law can and should be interpreted and applied in a way that promotes coherence and avoids conflict.⁷⁴ This principle is seen as a tool to address the increasing fragmentation of international law, characterized by the proliferation of specialized treaties and institutions.

One of the key manifestations of systemic integration is the interpretation of treaties in light of other relevant rules of international law. One of the main arguments of the Fragmentation Report was that the VCLT is well suited to deal with the complexities of the ever-growing body of international norms and the proliferation of international courts and tribunals.⁷⁵

Article 31(3)(c) VCLT⁷⁶ is often cited as embodying this principle, stating that “*there shall be taken into account, together with the context... any relevant rules of international law applicable in the relations between the parties*”.⁷⁷ This means that when interpreting a treaty, one should consider other relevant rules of international law, even if those rules are not explicitly mentioned in the treaty. Therefore, when interpreting a treaty, this provision requires interpreters to consider the broader normative environment of international law, even if the treaty itself does not explicitly refer to other rules. The rationale behind Art. 31(3)(c) VCLT is that the relationship between divergent rules of international law “can only be approached through a process of reasoning that makes them appear as parts of some coherent and meaningful whole”.⁷⁸ Having that in mind, it is not a coincidence that Martti

⁷⁴ Fragmentation Report, para. 1(1); Kwiecień, R., *General Principles of Law: The Gentle Guardians of Systemic Integration of International Law*, Polish Yearbook of International Law, 2017, p. 236.

⁷⁵ González Hauck, S., *Systemic Interpretation in International Law*, Doctoral Dissertation, University of St. Gallen, School of Management, Economics, Law, Social Sciences and International Affairs, 2019, pp. 5-7.

⁷⁶ Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties, 22 May 1969, 1155 UNTS 331.

⁷⁷ McLachlan, C., *The Principle of Systemic Integration and Article 31(3)(c) of the Vienna Convention*, *International and Comparative Law Quarterly*, Vol. 54, Issue 2, 2005, p. 280; Murphy, S. D., Murphy, S. D., *op. cit.*, pp. 295-296; Kammerhofer, J., *Systemic Integration, Legal Theory and the ILC*, *Finnish Yearbook of International Law*, Vol. 19, 2008, p. 158.

⁷⁸ Fragmentation Report, para. 414.

Koskenniemi (within the Study Group of the International Law Commission) chose the VCLT as the conceptual framework for analyzing the fragmentation of international law.⁷⁹

The principle is rooted in the idea that international law is not a collection of isolated rules, but rather a single system with interconnected parts.⁸⁰ As such, systemic integration helps reduce the risk of fragmentation, which occurs when different parts of international law develop in isolation from each other, potentially leading to conflicting or inconsistent rules.⁸¹ This principle has been invoked by scholars and tribunals to support the idea that international courts should consider the jurisprudence of other international courts and tribunals, even if they are not bound to reach the same conclusions.⁸² Systemic integration is seen as a way to ensure that different areas of international law work together harmoniously.⁸³

It allows for the interpretation of specific rules within a broader legal context,⁸⁴ promoting unity and coherence in the application of international law and avoiding conflicts between different norms.⁸⁵ By considering the broader legal landscape, systemic integration encourages a holistic and integrated approach to legal interpretation.⁸⁶ Having in mind such character-

⁷⁹ Fragmentation Report, para. 17.

⁸⁰ McLachlan, C., *op. cit.*, p. 280.

⁸¹ Peters, A., The refinement of international law: From fragmentation to regime interaction and politicization, *International Journal of Constitutional Law*, Vol. 15, Issue 3, 2017, pp. 692-693.

⁸² Declaration of Judge Greenwood was that: "International law is not a series of fragmented specialist and self-contained bodies of law, each of which functions in isolation from the others; it is a single, unified system of law and each international court can, and should, draw on the jurisprudence of other international courts and tribunals, even though it is not bound necessarily to come to the same conclusions," *Ahmadou Sadio Diallo (Republic Guinea v. Democratic Republic Congo)* (compensation owed by the Democratic Republic of the Congo to the Republic of Guinea), Judgment, 2012 ICJ Rep. 324 (June 19, 2012), Declaration of Judge Greenwood, para. 8.

⁸³ McLachlan, C., *op. cit.*, p. 280.

⁸⁴ "The trend has been to widen the use of Article 31(3)(c) of the VCLT to the point where it has become an important method to avoid the negative effects of the much-lamented fragmentation of international law and to limit the potential risk of norms, 'regimes' or tribunals entering into conflict with each other", Kammerhofer, J., *op. cit.*, p. 158.

⁸⁵ Ziegler, K. S., Beyond Pluralism and Autonomy: Systemic Harmonisation as a Paradigm for the Interaction of EU Law and International Law, *Yearbook of European Law*, Vol. 35, 2016, p. 669; Milanović, M., Norm Conflict in International Law: Whither Human Rights?, *Duke Journal of Comparative & International Law*, Vol. 20, 2009, pp. 72-74.

⁸⁶ Rachovitsa, A., The Principle of Systemic Integration in Human Rights Law, *International*

istics, there is a famous metaphore in percieving systemic integration as a master key to a large building, with which access to all rooms is achievable.⁸⁷

However, systemic integration in international law does not inherently resolve all conflicts between norms.⁸⁸ It is not a “one-size-fits-all” tool or a “universal panacea”.⁸⁹ It primarily acts as a means of conflict prevention by encouraging the interpretation of legal instruments in a way that considers and accommodates different objectives, interests, and values within the wider international legal system,⁹⁰ perceiving international law as a cohesive system with interconnected parts.

It is also important to stress out that systemic integration aims to harmonize the interpretation of legal rules, but it doesn’t necessarily dictate a specific outcome for that interpretation.⁹¹ Interpretation alone cannot resolve genuine conflicts between norms, a point acknowledged by scholars and the International Law Commission (ILC).⁹² When genuine conflicts arise, additional legal techniques are needed to determine which norm prevails. There are several factors which contribute to the limitations of systemic integration in fully resolving norm conflicts: 1) the positions of the parties involved might be too divergent, 2) there might be a significant clash of interests, 3) attempting to harmonize the norms could lead to sacrificing the interests of the weaker party. In such situations, systemic integration might not be sufficient to bridge the gap between conflicting norms.⁹³

and Comparative Law Quarterly, vol. 66, 2017, p.559.

⁸⁷ Campbell McLachlan has attributed this metaphor to ICJ Judge Xue Hanqin; McLachlan, C., *op. cit.*, p. 281. Scholars have referred to this rule as the ‘master-key’ to the house of international law; Peters, A., *Fragmentation and Constitutionalization*, In A. Orford and F. Hoffmann (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of the Theory of International Law*, Oxford University Press, 2016, p. 1012, 1025.

⁸⁸ Andenas, M., Ruben Leiss, J., Article 38(1)(d) ICJ Statute and the Principle of Systemic Institutional Integration, University of Oslo Faculty of Law Legal Studies Research Paper Series No. 2016-20, 2016, p. 16, available at: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2869655

⁸⁹ McLachlan, C., *The Principle of Systemic Integration and Article 31(3)(c) of the Vienna Convention*, *International and Comparative Law Quarterly*, Vol. 54, Issue 2, 2005, p. 318.

⁹⁰ Murphy, S. D., *op. cit.*, p. 307.

⁹¹ *Fragmentation Report*, para. 419.

⁹² McLachlan, C., *op. cit.*, p. 318; Pauwelyn, J., *op. cit.*, p. 272; Milanović, M., *Norm Conflict in International Law: Whither Human Rights?*, *Duke Journal of Comparative & International Law*, Vol. 20, 2009, p. 73; Kammerhofer, J., *op. cit.*, p. 165; *Fragmentation Report*, para. 410.

⁹³ For example, if a conflict arises between a treaty obligation and a Security Council resolution, the resolution generally takes precedence due to Article 103 of the UN Charter, which emphasizes the primacy of obligations under the Charter; Milanović, M., *Norm Conflict*

The systemic integration approach is tailored to fit the same type of international treaties - the one dealing with substantive rules, as the usual type of legal provisions in all matters except for Private International Law (e.g. Environmental Law, Human Rights Law, Trade Law, Law of the Sea, European Law, Investment Law, International Refugee Law, International Criminal Law etc). These *special regimes* were discussed in the Fragmentation Report.⁹⁴ The systematic approach could be also described as the “pick and choose” principle. However, the systemic integration approach does not seem to lead to an efficient and justified result when operating with considerably different Private International Law rules. Moreover, as we will see, it may raise serious concerns in some cases.

Let us test this approach on the example of the Serbian bilateral PIL treaty with Romania (1961) since the latter is also an EU Member State, while Serbia is an EU Candidate State. At the same time, Serbia and Romania are bound by both the 2007 Hague Maintenance Protocol and the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention. The hypothetical scenario goes like this: the child, a Romanian national, was born in a relationship of a Serbian-Romanian couple. The family moved from Romania to Serbia (Vojvodina). The relationship deteriorated, so the rights of custody, rights to access and the maintenance obligation arise before the Serbian court. The systemic integration approach, aligned with the *gentleman's clause* in the 2007 Hague Maintenance Protocol and the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention, would lead to the following result: bilateral treaty envisages the direct international jurisdiction (*forum nationalis* of the child or *forum domicilii/residendi* of the parties; depending on the circumstances of the case),⁹⁵ resulting in the international jurisdiction of the Serbian court regarding all the claims. Subsequently, the issue of applicable law for all three issues arise. Conflict-of-laws rules in the bilateral treaty refer to the State of the child's nationality in terms of right of custody, rights to access and the maintenance obligation.⁹⁶ In accordance with *ius sanguinis* principle, the child has double nationality (Romanian and Serbian). Now, the Serbian judge has to turn to the 1982 PIL Act in order to resolve the positive conflict of nationality, since all the bilateral PIL treaties binding Serbia had left this issue out. In accordance with the principle of exclusivity of the Serbian nationality,⁹⁷ the child is exclusively a Serbian

in International Law: Whither Human Rights?, Duke Journal of Comparative & International Law, Vol. 20, 2009, pp. 78-79.

⁹⁴ Fragmentation Report, para. 8, 15, Chapter II (C) paras 161-171.

⁹⁵ Article 27 of the Agreement.

⁹⁶ Article 26 of the Agreement.

⁹⁷ Article 11 (1) of the 1982 PIL Act.

national; thus, the substantive rules of 2005 Serbian Family Act⁹⁸ will apply to the merits of the case. The rights of custody is given solely to the mother by the judgment, while the father enjoys the rights to access, as arranged by the same judgement. Besides, the child is entitled to child support in a certain amount which the father has to pay every month. As the father resides in Romania, the issue of recognition and enforcement will have come to the fore. Its provisions prescribe *no ipso iure* recognition. Therefore, the control mechanism tackle the typical grounds for non-recognition in respect of the decision on the rights of custody and the rights of access.⁹⁹ Therefore, the control mechanism tackles the typical grounds for non-recognition: indirect international jurisdiction; judgment is no longer subject to the appeal; public policy exception; *res judicata* encompassing the judgment which is contrary to the previous judgment rendered between the same parties and on the same cause of action; the right of defence). In terms of the child support, the authors plead for application of the 2007 Hague Child Support Convention as the most favourable treaty. So far, so good. However, one may discuss that, in the light of the best interest of the child principle, the connecting factors of rules on international jurisdiction and applicable law in the relevant bilateral treaty *in abstracto* differ significantly from those envisaged in the 2007 Hague Maintenance Protocol and the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention. By ways of explanation, the best interest of the child is promoted and protected in both HCCH conventions by the territorialism principle, thus referring to the habitual residence of the child as the primary connecting factor in terms of international jurisdiction and applicable law.¹⁰⁰ Concerning the latter, when the issue of parental responsibility (rights of custody and rights of access) has to be decided on the merits of the case by the court, the best interest of the child coincides with the principle of parallelism of *forum* and *ius*. However, this principle is not an example of the *l'art pour l'art* maxim's admittance in Private International Law. The parallelism principle is subordinated to the best interest of the child principle and the preservation of the

⁹⁸ Family Act, *Official Gazette of the RS*, 18/2005, 72/2011, 6/215.

⁹⁹ Arts. 50-58 of the Agreement.

¹⁰⁰ Article 5 of the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention, as a rule on general international jurisdiction in parental responsibility matters. Lagarde, P., Explanatory Report, *Proceedings of the Eighteenth Session (1996)*, tome II, *Protection of children*, The Hague, 1996, 553-555. In the 2007 Hague Maintenance Protocol, the application of the law of the state in which the creditor has his/her habitual residence is the general rule in Article. However, the child support is regulated under the special regime of conflict-of-laws rules in Article (cascade or reversed cascade mechanism of conflict-of-laws rules). Bonomi, A., Explanatory Report, 29-31, 33-40, available at: <https://assets.hcch.net/docs/44d7912f-ce6d-487e-b3ac-65bbd14fe1b2.pdf>

closest connection principle in both HCCH conventions.¹⁰¹ On the other side, the bilateral treaty promotes the nationality principle as *in abstracto* tuned connecting factor to promote the best interest of the child who shares the ties with both states of the bilateral treaty. Still, the circumstances of this particular hypothetical case have convinced us that when the nationality and the habitual residence of the child coincide and refer to the same State, the conflict between the personal connecting factor (nationality) and the territorial connecting factor (habitual residence) with regard to protection of the best interest of the child turns into a whiter shade of pale.

However, let us now shake the kaleidoscope of the circumstances of our hypothetical case. If the rights of custody proceedings result in the deprivation of the parental rights of custody over a minor child and the child has to be placed in foster care, the deprivation of the rights of custody will still be decided by the rules of the bilateral treaty, while the foster care placement has to be decided by the rules of the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention, since the bilateral treaty does not provide a rule for this situation. While the decision on the deprivation of the rights of custody will have to be submitted to the requirements of the bilateral treaty in order to be recognized in Romania (general regime of the recognition and enforcement), the foster care placement decision could produce effects in Romania *ipso iure*, in accordance with the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention.¹⁰² In addition, the guardianship issue in this case has to be decided pursuant to the bilateral treaty, since it does envisage a rule on this issue.¹⁰³ The same is true for the decision on child support. And there we are, being unwillingly dragged into in the scenario of the movie “Everything Everywhere All at Once!” Indeed, the judge who manages to swim through the dark and turbulent Private International Law waters and to match all the international treaties’ puzzles should win the (judicial) Oscar. Otherwise, could we blame the judge if he/she turns the blind eye to the bilateral treaty, while hiding under the mechanism of the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention and the 2007 Hague Maintenance Protocol regarding rights of custody and rights of access and the law applicable to maintenance obligations in this case? Apart from judicial instinct, may we come to the same result, but relying on some legal ground?

¹⁰¹ Marjanović, S., *Legal Principles of the 1982 PIL Act and Filling the Legal Gaps in the Conflict of Laws Matter in Serbian Private International Law: A Different Perspective*, Annals of the Faculty of Law in Belgrade, No. 4/2024, 784-787.

¹⁰² Article 23 (1) of the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention.

¹⁰³ Arts. 30-32; and 50-58 of the Agreement.

3. Gentleman's clause and priority clause: the case of bilateral PIL treaties binding for Serbia and the EU Member States

The issues of coordination of the bilateral PIL treaties concurring the relevant HCCH conventions will result in a similar outcome of the application of other bilateral PIL treaties still in force in Serbia, but concluded within the period of former Yugoslavia. Even though the systemic integration approach could theoretically and practically work in the analyzed hypothetical case, it is rather questionable whether the outcome of this "treaties-puzzle" is efficient and justified. In other words, may we deviate from this type of "old" bilateral PIL treaties? The wording of the *gentleman's clauses* in the 2007 Hague Maintenance Protocol and the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention does not seem to leave a way out since they refer to the express joint declaration on the priority of the HCCH conventions as necessary. Most of these States became EU members, bringing the issue on an even more perplexed level.

The Regulation 664/2009 of 7 July 2009¹⁰⁴ and the Regulation 662/2009 of 17 July 2009¹⁰⁵ have established a procedure for the negotiation and conclusion of agreements between Member States and third countries concerning jurisdiction, recognition and enforcement of decisions in matrimonial matters, matters of parental responsibility and matters relating to maintenance obligations, and the law applicable to maintenance obligations (falling now under the Brussels II ter¹⁰⁶ regime and the Maintenance Regulation¹⁰⁷), as well as with regard to law applicable to contractual and non-contractual obligations (otherwise falling under the regulations Rome I¹⁰⁸ and Rome

¹⁰⁴ Council Regulation (EC) No 664/2009 of 7 July 2009 establishing a procedure for the negotiation and conclusion of agreements between Member States and third countries concerning jurisdiction, recognition and enforcement of judgments and decisions in matrimonial matters, matters of parental responsibility and matters relating to maintenance obligations, and the law applicable to matters relating to maintenance obligations, *OJ L 200*, 31.7.2009.

¹⁰⁵ Regulation (EC) No 662/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 July 2009 establishing a procedure for the negotiation and conclusion of agreements between Member States and third countries on particular matters concerning the law applicable to contractual and non-contractual obligations, *OJ L 200*, 31.7.2009.

¹⁰⁶ Council Regulation (EU) 2019/1111 of 25 June 2019 on jurisdiction, the recognition and enforcement of decisions in matrimonial matters and the matters of parental responsibility, and on international child abduction (recast), ST/8214/2019/INIT, *OJ L 178*, 2.7.2019.

¹⁰⁷ Council Regulation (EC) No 4/2009 of 18 December 2008 on jurisdiction, applicable law, recognition and enforcement of decisions and cooperation in matters relating to maintenance obligations, *OJ L 7*, 10.1.2009.

¹⁰⁸ Regulation (EC) No 593/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June

II¹⁰⁹). However, the negotiation process is quite long in these cases. The rare example when this was allowed is the bilateral PIL treaty between France and Algeria. It is not easy to find a similar situation which resulted in the Council's official authorization of France to negotiate the bilateral treaty in accordance with the Regulation 664/2009 of 7 July 2009. In 2023, the Council empowered France to negotiate a bilateral agreement with Algeria on matters related to judicial cooperation concerning family law matters.¹¹⁰ Reading between the lines, it seems to us that a high number of French nationals residing in Algeria was one of the key factors for deciding on the authorization.¹¹¹ Moreover, Algeria will never become an EU State, while Serbia enjoys a candidate State status, as well as other states (without any anticipation of the outcome of enlargement). Even in the case of the France and Algeria bilateral treaty, it took the European Commission (regarding the Proposal) and the Council (regarding the decision) seven years to reach the decision, having in mind that the Algerian initiative was passed in 2016.¹¹² In fact, in 2012 Slovakia initiated negotiations with Serbia on the same issues, relying on the Regulation 664/2009.¹¹³ Yet, Slovakia eventually quietly withdrew from the process. The European Council remained silent on this issue, most likely expecting the immediate application of the EU *acquis* following the enlargement. As time goes by, the question of when Serbia will become an EU member state turns into the question of whether Serbia will become a member. What to do in the meantime? Let us discuss some of the possible solutions.

3.1. *Lex specialis rule*

The principle of *lex specialis derogat legi generali* stand as a widely recognized maxim within legal interpretation and conflict resolution in interna-

2008 on the law applicable to contractual obligations (Rome I), *OJ L* 177, 4.7.2008.

¹⁰⁹ Regulation (EC) No 864/2007 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 July 2007 on the law applicable to non-contractual obligations (Rome II), *OJ L* 199, 31.07.2007.

¹¹⁰ Procedure 2023/0027/CNS, COM (2023) 64: Proposal for a COUNCIL DECISION on an authorisation addressed to France to negotiate a bilateral agreement with Algeria on matters related to judicial cooperation concerning family law matters (Adopted act: 32024D0592).

¹¹¹ European Commission, Proposal for a Council Decision on an authorisation addressed to France to negotiate a bilateral agreement with Algeria on matters related to judicial cooperation concerning family law matters, Brussels, 8.2.2023 COM(2023) 64 final 2023/0027 (CNS).

¹¹² *Ibid*, p. 1.

¹¹³ Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Serbia, the Department for international and European law, Document No. 018-05-3/13 of 19.02.2013, sent to the Council for Private International Law of the Serbian Government.

tional law.¹¹⁴ It dictates that when a matter is subject to regulation by both a general standard and a more specific rule, the latter should take precedence over the former.¹¹⁵ The relationship between the general standard and the specific rule, however, can be understood in two primary ways. First, the specific rule operates as an elaboration, update, or technical specification of the general standard. In this scenario, both the specific and general rules essentially aim toward the same objective. This concept aligns with the already mentioned principle of harmonization, which encourages interpreting seemingly conflicting legal rules in a way that maximizes their compatibility. In the second scenario, the specific rule acts as a genuine exception to the general standard, creating a conflict that needs resolution. The application of *lex specialis* often involves analyzing the intent of the parties involved, particularly through examining the treaty texts. This examination helps determine whether the special rule aims to *supplement* or *derogate* from the general law. The principle of *lex specialis* acknowledges the inherent hierarchy within legal systems, where more specific rules, often crafted to address unique circumstances, are deemed to better reflect the intent of the parties and offer more effective regulation. On the other hand, the rule of later law overrides prior law is also often used in order to resolve conflicts of norms.

By testing different approaches in the specific hypothetical case, we ended with two of them - *lex generalis* and *lex specialis* rule aligned with *lex posterior* and *lege priori* rule. Yet, the first issue we faced was an issue of successive treaties. In the case of Serbia, bilateral PIL treaties have no provisions on the scope of application *ratione materiae*, nor *ratione personae*.¹¹⁶ Regarding the *ratione materiae* issue, one can come to this conclusion only after reading all the bilateral treaty's provisions. Besides, it should be borne in mind that the bilateral PIL treaties are fragmentary-oriented towards Private International Law matters, reminding us again of a "pick and chose" match. In most general terms, the bilateral PIL treaties binding Serbia could be classified in two groups: a) on legal assistance (often comprising some conflict-of-laws rules in family relations, status relations of natural persons,

¹¹⁴ Koskeniemi, M., The ILC Report, Study on the Function and Scope of the Lex Specialis rule and the Question of 'Self-Contained Regimes', 4 ILC, 7 May 2004, ILC(LVI)SG/ FIL/ CRD.1, para. 21.

¹¹⁵ Fragmentation Report, paras 56-59.

¹¹⁶ With the exception of the bilateral PIL treaty between Serbia and Turkey, but this treaty is one of the newest, while we are discussing the "old socialistic" bilateral PIL treaties. Agreement between the Republic of Serbia and the Republic of Turkey on mutual legal assistance in civil and commercial matters dated June 5, 2013, *Official Gazette of the RS - International Agreements*, No. 15/2015.

and succession issues with or without corresponding rules on international jurisdiction, and the recognition and enforcement); and b) recognition and enforcement (introducing the general regimes, or special regimes). Except for the treaty with Turkey, no other bilateral PIL treaty envisages any of the compatibility clauses - even the bilateral treaty with Turkey relies on the *gentlemen's clause*.¹¹⁷ Interpretation of the bilateral treaties as a *lex specialis* is deeply rooted in the Serbian legal system, almost as a Holy Scripture.¹¹⁸ Even though the Fragmentation Report does mention bilateral treaties as an example of *lex specialis*, when comparing the bilateral PIL treaties and the two HCCH conventions in terms of their essence, we came to an unforeseen conclusion. Their essence is the scope of application *ratione materiae*, regardless of the number of contracting states. However, this approach is justified *only* when the same states are contracting parties of the concurrent bilateral PIL treaties and the relevant HCCH convention envisaging the gentleman's clause. So, when comparing the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention and the 2007 Maintenance Protocol with the successive "old" bilateral PIL treaties binding for Serbia and some of the EU Member States, the latter appear to be *lex generalis*. Although fragmentary-oriented, and despite the fact that the conclusion on their scope of application *ratione materiae* comes only as a result of interpretation of the whole bilateral treaty, their scope of application is much broader than those in the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention and the 2007 Hague Maintenance Protocol. Moreover, the relevant HCCH conventions which regulate conflict of jurisdictions (with or without the conflict-of-laws rules) in certain family relations, could be *de facto* perceived as a network of bilateral treaties due to the system of objection to the accession of a new Contracting State.¹¹⁹ When we follow this idea, we actually compare treaties binding the same states as two bilateral treaties - a bilateral treaty as a general one (*lex generalis*), and the HCCH conventions as a special one (*lex specialis*).

Even if one does not agree with this authors' interpretation, strictly adhering to the thesis that bilateral treaties are in fact *lex specialis*, then one must resort to a different method of interpretation and conflict resolution

¹¹⁷ Article 24 of the bilateral PIL treaty with Turkey.

¹¹⁸ Đorđević and Dimitrijević rely on the *lex posterior rule* regarding bilateral treaties. Đorđević, S., Dimitrijević, D., *Pravo međunarodnih ugovora* (Law of international treaties), Institut za međunarodnu politiku i privredu, Beograd, 2011, p. 216.

¹¹⁹ E.g. Article 58 (3) of the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention and Article 58 (5) of the 2007 Hague Maintenance Convention. However, the latter envisages clear provision *on most effective rule* which serves as a legal ground to circumvent the systematic integration approach in favor of the application of the most favourable regime (Article 52 of the 2007 Hague Maintenance Convention).

altogether. Namely, in such a constellation, one turns to the argument of the “fall”, or decline in the value and relevance of the *lex specialis* maxim in favor of the *lex favorabilis* principle.¹²⁰ Therefore, the *lex specialis* principle is not always considered to be the appointed tool in norm-conflict resolution due to its conceptual vagueness,¹²¹ but gives way to other technics and/or tools – in this specific case, the underrated most favourable rule principle, which serves more as a technique of interpretation, than a principle, in order to avoid the conflict of norms. This would be a value-oriented approach in the decision as to the selection of the issue of priority of treaties.¹²²

3.2. *Lex posterior rule*

Lex priori is a general rule on the hierarchy of international treaties, while *lex posterior* is a special one. So, in the case of the “old” bilateral PIL treaties still binding Serbia and the EU Member State, while the same states are also bound by the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention or the 2007 Hague Maintenance Protocol, do we actually have two States, bound by an “old socialistic” bilateral PIL treaty (*as general and prior*) and one of these two HCCH conventions (*as special and posterior*), demonstrating *de facto* (or even *de iure*) their joint intention to supersede *lex priori*? In other words, why would we prefer yesterday over tomorrow, when “old” bilateral PIL treaties do not introduce any privileged regime actually justifying its status of *lex specialis*, nor do they increase legal certainty (as a general legal principle), nor rely on *in favorem victimae* principle or its alter ego - the best interest of the child (in cases involving children)? In fact, they are out-dated and fragmented. Let us bring to your attention once more the fact that at the time when most of these “old” bilateral PIL treaties were concluded with the specific EU Member State, the 1982 PIL Act as a *lex generalis* did not exist.¹²³ In these circumstances, the intention was to deviate from other national legislations partially regulating PIL matters or to fill in the gaps.

¹²⁰ One may observe a trend towards rejecting the application of a specialized rule in favor of other interpretation techniques in some international sub-regimes, or their intersection, such as the intersection of international human rights law and international humanitarian law. Milanović, M., A Norm Conflict Perspective on the Relationship between International Humanitarian Law and Human Rights Law, 14, 3, 2010, Journal of Conflict & Security Law, p. 460, 479.

¹²¹ Lindroos, A., Addressing Norm Conflicts in a Fragmented Legal System: The Doctrine of the *Lex Specialis*, 2005, 74, 1, Nordic Journal of International Law, p. 27.

¹²² Kolb, R., The Law of Treaties, Edward Elgar Publishing Limited, 2023, p. 214.

¹²³ With the exception of the bilateral PIL treaty concluded with Cyprus in 1988 and later on with Croatia in 1997.

Furthermore, conflict-of-laws rules and rules on direct international jurisdiction relating to the parents-children legal relations in some of these “old” bilateral PIL treaties became contrary to the Serbian public policy. Back in the 1992, the Constitution of the then FRY introduced the principle of equality in terms of the right of children born out of wedlock.¹²⁴ When the Convention on the rights of the child (CRC)¹²⁵ came into force at the international level in September 1990, the best interest of the child principle made its first steps towards integration in the international public policy principle. Therefore, the relevant provisions prescribed in the “old” bilateral PIL treaties with Bulgaria,¹²⁶ and Greece¹²⁷ became null and void (*ex nunc*). The reason could be found not only in the CRC, but in the EU Charter on Fundamental Human Rights.¹²⁸ The best interest of the child is a general principle of the EU law, deriving from the Treaty of the European Union.¹²⁹ Hence, when analyzing other “old” bilateral PIL treaties which survived this public policy test, in the majority of those treaties, the special protection of the children is tailored to fit it *in abstracto* by means of nationality as the primary connecting factor.

Finally, taking into consideration that the joint declaration on the priority of the relevant HCCH convention implies the long process of formal diplomatic negotiations, could we suppose that the States have already manifested their intention to supersede the prior treaty and apply the relevant HCCH convention even without providing this declaration? Otherwise, would the *gentlemen's clause* be too formal or too stringent, thus leading to over-

¹²⁴ “Children born out of wedlock enjoy the same rights as the children born in wedlock.” Article 62(2) of the Constitution of the FRY, *Official Gazette of the FRY*, No. 1/92, 34/92 - Amendment I and 29/2000 - Amendment II-IX, Article 62(2).

¹²⁵ *Official Gazette of the SFRY - International Agreements*, No. 15/90 and *Official Gazette of the - International Agreements*, No. 4/96 and 2/97.

¹²⁶ Art. 38; applicable law on legal relations between the father and an illegitimate child.

¹²⁷ Art. 22; law applicable to legal relations between the father and his illegitimate child. Although not an EU Member State, it should be noted that bilateral PIL treaty with Russia also makes the discrimination between children depending on their parents marital or extra-marital status (Art. 27: law applicable to legal relations between the mother and her illegitimate child; Art. 28: direct international jurisdiction for disputes on legal relations between the mother and her illegitimate child).

¹²⁸ Article 24(2) of the EU Charter (Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, *OJ C 326*, 26 October 2012).

¹²⁹ Article 6(3) TEU. See on details Goldner Lang, I., *The Child's Best Interests as a Gap Filler and Expander of EU Law in Internal Situations*, In K. Ziegler, P. Neuvonen and V. Moreno-Lax (eds.), *Research Handbook on General Principles of EU Law*, Edward Elgar Publishing, 2019, available at https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3579335, pp. 2-7.

regulation? In the case of the EU Member States, the formal initiative is most unlikely to ensue. Moreover, in its decision regarding France and Algeria, the European Commission emphasized the significance of multilateralism, embodied in HCCH conventions:

“However, while recognizing the exceptional economic, cultural, historical, social and political ties between France and Algeria, the Commission remarked that, in its judicial cooperation with third States, the EU broadly relies on the existing multilateral framework, such as the one created by the Hague Conference on Private International Law (HCCH). This ensures that the same legal framework applies to a large number of States with different legal backgrounds and offers considerable benefits. Therefore, the EU promotes the accession of its partner States – in particular, the Mediterranean countries such as Algeria - to the relevant international conventions in the civil justice area, many of which were drawn up by the HCCH.”¹³⁰

In this way, it seems that the European Commission has expressly articulated the EU’s intention to *informally amend* the bilateral treaties of its Member States with third countries, while expecting that the third states will join those HCCH conventions which are part of the *acquis communautaire*.

4. Conclusion

With the fragmentation of international law, its “normative explosion”, and ever-growing number of international treaties in an array of spheres, the probability of both conflict of norms and conflict of regimes increases significantly. Hence, number of legal orders and sub-regimes exist in a “normative jungle”, leading to a growing need for the existence of a plethora of technics and tools to overcome problems of conflicts.

In the very specific (and even exotic) state of affairs of the intertwines of multilateral and bilateral treaties in Serbian Private International Law arena, we are faced with numerous problematic situations. Unfortunately, when faced with a situation where concurrent multilateral and bilateral treaties do not regulate their mutual relationship via different types of clauses, one must find the appropriate legal answer. Firstly, systemic integration provides us with the necessary tool for avoiding the conflict of norms altogether. Even though it encourages a more holistic approach to legal interpretation, it’s not a guaranteed solution for *all* conflicts in international law. This is pain-

¹³⁰ European Commission, Proposal for a Council Decision on an authorisation addressed to France to negotiate a bilateral agreement with Algeria on matters related to judicial cooperation concerning family law matters, Brussels, 8.2.2023 COM (2023) 64 final 2023/0027 (CNS), pp. 1-2.

fully evident in the sphere of Private International Law and even more so in the specific situations of the intersection of the analyzed HCCH conventions and “old” bilateral PIL treaties involving cross-border family matters in the Republic of Serbia, specifically in cases when the other Contracting Party is an EU member State. When addressing the issue of conflicts of norms, the *lex specialis* and *lex posterior* rules are the most prominent. However, the application of the *lex specialis* rule does not always provide for an adequate solution. Therefore, one must turn to other technics and tools of conflict avoidance, conflict resolution and interpretation.

Even though the nucleus of this paper may seem as a local or regional issue, regarding a small number of countries emanating from the former Yugoslavia, it can also serve as a cautionary tale and/or constructive approach on the situation that when life gives you lemons – all you can do is to make lemonade. Additionally, the logic of problem-solving could be transferred to other parts of the world which face or could face a similar issue. Confronted with the legal problem of a strange combination of simultaneous existence of multiple international treaties between the same Contracting Parties that regulate the subject of family law relations in different ways, the authors attempted to find a more adequate legal solution than what would be achieved by following the usual footsteps. It cannot be stressed enough that this paper was more of a practical, then a pure theoretical mental acrobatic exercise, due to the specifics of the case of Serbia at hand. One way of academic discourse would be simply choosing to criticize the strategy of the Serbian government in persistently concluding bilateral PIL treaties envisaging the conflict-of-laws rules, rules on international jurisdiction or recognition and enforcement regimes which play a “puzzle-game” with the analysed HCCH convention instead of just applying HCCH conventions. However, that is a path not chosen, because such a negative approach would not give much needed practical answers. Therefore, one must find a way though the Gordian knot by a radicalization of arguments, in order to avoid the application of the “old” bilateral PIL treaties in favour of the HCCH conventions.

Summary

The “old” bilateral PIL treaties binding Serbia as a Candidate State of the EU membership, and the States which is a part of the EU, are fragmentary-oriented and old-dated. Besides, most of them were concluded before the adoption of the ex-Yugoslav 1982 PIL Act as *lex generalis* (which is still in force in Serbia and Bosnia and Herzegovina). Their concurrent HCCH conventions, more precisely the 1996 Hague Children Protection Convention

and the 2007 Hague Maintenance Protocol, envisage the gentlemen's clause while introducing the possibility of joint declaration on the primacy of the relevant HCCH convention. When it comes to the "old" bilateral PIL treaties between Serbia and States which afterwards become a part of the EU, these bilateral treaties stem from the period of the FPRY and SFRY. The negotiation process in order to give joint declaration on the supremacy of the relevant HCCH convention in most unlikely to happen. Therefore, the authors try to set aside the usual criteria - number of contracting states and to take a deep look into the scope of application *ratione materiae* of these treaties. Then the bilateral PIL treaties appear as *lex generali* since their scope of application is much broader than the scope of application of the HCCH convention. This result is true only when comparing the treaties in the specific case - when both states are contracting parties of the "old" bilateral PIL treaty and the concurrent HCCH convention. Simultaneous application of the *lex specialis* approach and *lex posterior* rule, we came to the conclusion that these principles could solve the issue of the chaotic mosaic of the PIL rules in some cross-broader family relations. This mosaic as a result of the systematic integration approach is in these cases contrary to the best interest of the child principle and the legal certainty principle. However, if the gentlemen's clause should be formally followed, then the chaotic mosaic cannot be circumvented when needed for the sake of efficient and justified outcome.

References

Andenas, M., Ruben Leiss, J., Article 38(1)(d) ICJ Statute and the Principle of Systemic Institutional Integration, University of Oslo Faculty of Law Legal Studies Research Paper Series No. 2016-20, 2016, available at: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2869655

Aust, A., *Modern Treaty Law and Practice*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2000;

Bonomi, A., Explanatory Report, 29-31, 33-40, available at: <https://assets.hcch.net/docs/44d7912f-ce6d-487e-b3ac-65bbd14fe1b2.pdf>

Blanca Noodt Taquela, M., *Applying the Most Favourable Treaty or Domestic Rules to Facilitate Private International Law Co-Operation*, Collected Courses of the Hague Academy of International Law, Vol. 377, Brill|Nijhoff, 2015;

Czapliński, W., Danilenko, G., Conflicts of norms in international law, *Netherlands Yearbook of International Law*, vol. XXI, 1990, pp. 3-42;

Goldner Lang, I., *The Child's Best Interests as a Gap Filler and Expander*

of EU Law in Internal Situations, In K. Ziegler, P. Neuvonen and V. Moreno-Lax (eds.), *Research Handbook on General Principles of EU Law*, Edward Elgar Publishing, 2019, available at: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3579335

González Hauck, S., *Systemic Interpretation in International Law*, Doctoral Dissertation, University of St. Gallen, School of Management, Economics, Law, Social Sciences and International Affairs, 2019;

Jenks, W. C., *The conflict of law-making treaties*, *British Yearbook of International Law*, Vol. 30, 1953, pp. 401-453;

Kammerhofer, J., *Systemic Integration, Legal Theory and the ILC*, *Finnish Yearbook of International Law*, Vol. 19, 2008, pp. 157-182;

Kolb, R., *The Law of Treaties*, Edward Elgar Publishing Limited, 2023;

Kwiecień, R., *General Principles of Law: The Gentle Guardians of Systemic Integration of International Law*, *Polish Yearbook of International Law*, 2017, pp. 235-242;

Lagarde, P., *Explanatory report on the 1996 HCCH Child Protection Convention. Proceedings of the Eighteenth Session (1996)*, tome II, *Protection of children*. Hague: HCCH, 1996;

Lindroos, A., *Addressing Norm Conflicts in a Fragmented Legal System: The Doctrine of the Lex Specialis*, 2005, 74, 1, *Nordic Journal of International Law*, pp. 27-66;

Marjanović, S., *Legal Principles of the 1982 PIL ACT and Filling the Legal Gaps in the Conflict of Laws Matter in Serbian Private International Law: A Different Perspective*, *Annals of the Faculty of Law in Belgrade*, No. 4/2024;

McLachlan, C., *The Principle of Systemic Integration and Article 31(3) (c) of the Vienna Convention*, *International and Comparative Law Quarterly*, Vol. 54, Issue 2, 2005, pp. 279-320;

Milanović, M., *A Norm Conflict Perspective on the Relationship between International Humanitarian Law and Human Rights Law*, 14, 3, 2010, *Journal of Conflict & Security Law*, pp. 459-483;

Milanović, M., *Norm Conflict in International Law: Whither Human Rights?*, *Duke Journal of Comparative & International Law*, Vol. 20, 2009, pp. 69-132;

Murphy, S. D., *Deconstructing Fragmentation: Koskenniemi's 2006 ILC Project*, *Temple International & Comparative Law Journal*, Vol. 27, Issue 2, 2013, pp. 293-308;

Pauwelyn, J., *Conflict of Norms in Public International Law: How WTO*

Law Relates to Other Rules of International Law, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2003;

Peters, A., Fragmentation and Constitutionalization, In A. Orford and F. Hoffmann (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of the Theory of International Law*, Oxford University Press, 2016;

Peters, A., The refinement of international law: From fragmentation to regime interaction and politicization, *International Journal of Constitutional Law*, Vol. 15, Issue 3, 2017, 671-704;

Rachovitsa, A., The Principle of Systemic Integration in Human Rights Law, *International and Comparative Law Quarterly*, vol. 66, 2017, pp. 557-588;

Ziegler, K. S., Beyond Pluralism and Autonomy: Systemic Harmonisation as a Paradigm for the Interaction of EU Law and International Law, *Yearbook of European Law*, Vol. 35, 2016, pp. 667-711;

Đorđević, S., Dimitrijević, D., *Pravo međunarodnih ugovora* (Law of international treaties), Institut za međunarodnu politiku i privredu, Beograd, 2011.

Regulations

European Commission, Proposal for a Council Decision on an authorisation addressed to France to negotiate a bilateral agreement with Algeria on matters related to judicial cooperation concerning family law matters, Brussels, 8.2.2023 COM (2023) 64 final 2023/0027 (CNS).

Protocol on the Law Applicable to Maintenance Obligations, *Official Gazette of the RS - International Agreements*, 1/2013.

Convention on Protection of Children and Co-operation in Respect of Intercountry Adoption, *Official Gazette of RS - International Agreements*, 12/2013.

Convention on Jurisdiction, Applicable Law, Recognition, Enforcement and Co-operation in respect of Parental Responsibility and Measures for the Protection of Children, *Official Gazette of RS - International Treaties*, 20/2015.

Convention on the International Recovery of Child Support and Other Forms of Family Maintenance, *Official Gazette of RS - International Agreements*, 4/2020.

Agreement on trade and navigation between the Kingdom of Serbs, Croats and Slovenians (SCS) and the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Ireland, *Official Gazette*, 46/1928

Convention between the Kingdom of Yugoslavia and Great Britain on the arrangement of mutual assistance in conducting proceedings in civil and

commercial matters pending or which may be pending before the respective judicial authorities, *Official Gazette*, 116/1937.

Trade agreement between Serbia and the United States of America, *Serbian Official Gazette*, 268/1882.

Convention on settlement and consular relations between Serbia and Switzerland, *Official Gazette*, 83/1888.

Agreement on trade and navigation between the Kingdom of Yugoslavia and the Kingdom of the Netherlands, *Official Gazette of the Kingdom of Yugoslavia*, 85-XXXVII/32.

Convention on Civil Procedure, *Official Gazette of the FPRY – International Treaties and other Agreements*, 6/1962.

Convention on Abolishing the Requirement of Legalisation for Foreign Public Documents, *Official Gazette of the FPRY – International Treaties and other Agreements*, 10/1962.

Convention on the Conflicts of Laws Relating to the Form of Testamentary Dispositions, *Official Gazette of the FPRY – supplement*, 11/1962.

Convention on the Law Applicable to Traffic Accidents, *Official Gazette of the SFRY – supplement* 26/1976.

Convention on the Law Applicable to Products Liability, *Official Gazette of the SFRY – International Agreements*, 8/1977.

Convention on International Access to Justice, *Official Gazette of the SFRY – International Treaties* 4/1988.

Convention on the Civil Aspects of International Child Abduction, *Official Gazette of the SFRY – International Treaties*, 7/1991.

Agreement on Legal Assistance between the FPR Yugoslavia and the Romanian People's Republic (1960) - Official Gazette of the FPRY - Supplement International Treaties 8 /1961.

Agreement on the Regulation of Legal Relations in Civil, Family and Criminal Matters between the SFR Yugoslavia and Czechoslovakia SR (1964) - Official Gazette of the SFRY - Supplement International Treaties 13/1964.

Agreement on Legal Relations in Civil and Criminal Matters between the FPR Yugoslavia and PR Poland (1960) - (Official Gazette of the FPRY - Supplement International Treaties 5 /1963)

Agreement on Mutual Legal Relations between the SFR Yugoslavia and the People's Republic of Hungary (1968), amended (1986) - (Official Gazette of the SFRY – Supplement International Treaties 3 /1968; with amendments – Official Gazette of the SFRY – Supplement International Treaties 1 / 1987)

Agreement on Mutual Legal Assistance between the FPR Yugoslavia and the People's Republic of Bulgaria (1956), *Official Gazette of the SFRY - Supplement International Treaties* 1/1957.

Agreement on Legal Assistance between the SFRY Yugoslavia and the Republic of Cyprus (1984), *Official Gazette of the SFRY - Supplement International Treaties* 2/1986).

Agreement on Legal Assistance in Civil, Family and Criminal Matters between the FPR Yugoslavia and DPR Algeria (1982), *Official Gazette of the FPRY, Supplement International Treaties* 2/1981.

Agreement on Legal Assistance between the SFRY Yugoslavia and the Republic of Cyprus (1984), *Official Gazette of the SFRY - Supplement International Treaties* 2/1986.

Agreement on legal and judicial cooperation between SFRY and the Republic of Iraq (1986), *Official Gazette of the SFRY - Supplement International Treaties* 1/1987.

Agreement on Legal Assistance in Civil, Family and Criminal Matters between the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia and the Mongolian People's Republic (1981), *Official Gazette of the SFRY - Supplement International Treaties*, 7 / 1982

Agreement between Yugoslavia and Iran on Mutual Exemption from *Cautio iudicatum solvi*, *Official Gazette of the FPRY - Supplement International Treaties*, 2/1957.

Agreement on trade and navigation between FPR Yugoslavia and Japan, *Official Gazette of the FPRY - Supplement*, 7/1959.

Agreement on reciprocal recognition of the diplomatic-consular form of marriage between Yugoslavia and Norway, *Official Gazette of the FPRY - International Treaties and other agreements*, 6/1958.

Convention on Mutual Legal Relations between the FPR Yugoslavia and the Kingdom of Greece (1959), *Official Gazette of the FPRY - Supplement International Treaties* 7/1960.

Agreement on Mutual Recognition and Enforcement of Court Decisions between the SFR Yugoslavia and the Kingdom of Greece, *Official Gazette of the SFRY, Supplement International Treaties* 6/1960.

Convention on Mutual Legal Relations between the FPR Yugoslavia and the Republic of Austria (1954), *Official Gazette of the FPRY - Supplement International Treaties* 8/1955.

Agreement on mutual recognition and enforcement of decisions on

maintenance between FPR Yugoslavia and the Republic of Austria (1961), Official Gazette of the SFRY, 2/1963.

Agreement on mutual recognition and enforcement of decisions of chosen courts and settlements concluded before the chosen courts in commercial matters between the FPR Yugoslavia and the Republic of Austria (1960), Official Gazette of the SFRY, 5/1961.

Convention on Issuing Documents on Personal Status and on Exemption from Legalization between SFR Yugoslavia and the Republic of France, Official Gazette of the SFRY - International treaties and other agreements, 3/1971.

Convention on the recognition and enforcement of court decisions in civil and commercial matters between the SFR Yugoslavia and the Republic of France (1971), Official Gazette of the SFRY - Supplement, 7/1972.

Convention on Jurisdiction and the Applicable Law in the Matters of Personal and Family Law between the SFR Yugoslavia and the Republic of France (1971) - (Official Gazette of the SFRY - Supplement International Treaties 55/1972.

Agreement on Facilitating the Application of the Hague Convention on Civil Procedure of March 1, 1954 between the SFR Yugoslavia and the Republic of France, Official Gazette of the SFRY - Supplement International Treaties and other agreements, 21/1971.

Agreement on legal assistance in civil and commercial matters between the SFR Yugoslavia and the Kingdom of Belgium, Official Gazette of the SFRY - Supplement International Treaties and other agreements, 7/1974.

Convention on the recognition and enforcement of court decisions on maintenance between the SFR Yugoslavia and the Kingdom of Belgium, Official Gazette of the SFRY - Supplement International Treaties and other agreements, 45/1976.

Convention on Issuing Extracts from Registers and Exemption from Legalization between the SFR Yugoslavia and the Kingdom of Belgium, Official Gazette of the SFRY, 55/1972.

Convention between the Kingdom of the SCS and Italy on the legal and judicial protection of the respective citizens, Official Gazette of the Kingdom of Yugoslavia, 42/1931.

Convention on mutual legal assistance in civil and administrative matters between the FPR of Yugoslavia and the Italian Republic, Official Gazette of the SFRY - International treaties and other agreements, 7/1974.

Convention on trade and navigation between the FNR of Yugoslavia and the Italian Republic, Official Gazette - Supplement, 14/1956.

Act on Resolving Conflict of Laws with the Regulations of other Countries, *Official Gazette of the SFRY*, 43/82 and 72/82 - corr., *Official Gazette of the FRY*, 46/96 and *Official Gazette of the of the RS*, 46/2006.

Agreement between the FR Yugoslavia and the Republic of Croatia on legal assistance in civil and criminal matters (1997), *Official Gazette of the FRY - International treaties*, 1/1998.

Convention on Taking of Evidence Abroad in Civil and Commercial matters, *Official Gazette of the RS – International Treaties* 1/2010 and 13/2013.

Convention on the Service Abroad of Judicial and Extrajudicial Documents in Civil or Commercial Matters, *Official Gazette of the RS – International Agreements* 1/2010 and 13/2013.

Agreement between the Republic of Serbia and Bosnia and Herzegovina on Amendments to the Agreement on Legal Assistance in Civil and Criminal Matters (2005), *Official Gazette of the Serbia and Montenegro - International treaties*, 6/2005, as amended (2010), *Official Gazette of the RS - International Treaties*, 13/2010.

Agreement between the Republic of Serbia and the Republic of Slovenia on legal assistance in civil and criminal matters (2011), *Official Gazette of the RS - International Treaties*, 9/2011.

Agreement between the Republic of Serbia and the Republic of Macedonia on legal assistance in civil and criminal matters (2012), *Official Gazette of the RS - International Treaties*, 5/2012.

Agreement between the Republic of Serbia and Montenegro on legal assistance in civil and criminal matters (2009), *Official Gazette of the RS - International Treaties*, 1/2010.

Agreement between the Republic of Serbia and the Republic of Belarus on legal assistance in civil and criminal matters (2013), *Official Gazette of the RS - International Treaties*, 13/2013.

Agreement between the Republic of Serbia and the Republic of Turkey on mutual legal assistance in civil and commercial matters (2015), *Official Gazette of the RS - International Treaties*, 15/2015.

Agreement on legal and judicial cooperation in civil and commercial matters between the Republic of Serbia and the United Arab Emirates (2023), *Official Gazette of the RS - International Treaties*, 7/2022.

Council Regulation (EC) No 664/2009 of 7 July 2009 establishing a procedure for the negotiation and conclusion of agreements between Member States and third countries concerning jurisdiction, recognition and enforcement of judgments and decisions in matrimonial matters, matters of parental

responsibility and matters relating to maintenance obligations, and the law applicable to matters relating to maintenance obligations, *OJ L 200*, 31.7.2009.

Regulation (EC) No 662/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 July 2009 establishing a procedure for the negotiation and conclusion of agreements between Member States and third countries on particular matters concerning the law applicable to contractual and non-contractual obligations, *OJ L 200*, 31.7.2009.

Council Regulation (EU) 2019/1111 of 25 June 2019 on jurisdiction, the recognition and enforcement of decisions in matrimonial matters and the matters of parental responsibility, and on international child abduction (recast), *ST/8214/2019/INIT*, *OJ L 178*, 2.7.2019.

Council Regulation (EC) No 4/2009 of 18 December 2008 on jurisdiction, applicable law, recognition and enforcement of decisions and cooperation in matters relating to maintenance obligations, *OJ L 7*, 10.1.2009.

Regulation (EC) No 593/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008 on the law applicable to contractual obligations (Rome I), *OJ L 177*, 4.7.2008.

Regulation (EC) No 864/2007 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 July 2007 on the law applicable to non-contractual obligations (Rome II), *OJ L 199*, 31.07.2007.

Procedure 2023/0027/CNS, COM (2023) 64: Proposal for a COUNCIL DECISION on an authorisation addressed to France to negotiate a bilateral agreement with Algeria on matters related to judicial cooperation concerning family law matters (Adopted act: 32024D0592).

Agreement between the Republic of Serbia and the Republic of Turkey on mutual legal assistance in civil and commercial matters dated June 5, 2013, *Official Gazette of the RS - International Agreements*, No. 15/2015 Council Regulation (EC) No 664/2009 of 7 July 2009 establishing a procedure for the negotiation and conclusion of agreements between Member States and third countries concerning jurisdiction, recognition and enforcement of judgments and decisions in matrimonial matters, matters of parental responsibility and matters relating to maintenance obligations, and the law applicable to matters relating to maintenance obligations, *OJ L 200*, 31.7.2009.

Regulation (EC) No 662/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 July 2009 establishing a procedure for the negotiation and conclusion of agreements between Member States and third countries on particular matters concerning the law applicable to contractual and non-contractual obligations, *OJ L 200*, 31.7.2009.

Regulation (EC) No 593/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008 on the law applicable to contractual obligations (Rome I), *OJ L* 177, 4.7.2008.

Regulation (EC) No 864/2007 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 July 2007 on the law applicable to non-contractual obligations (Rome II), *OJ L* 199, 31.07.2007.

Council Regulation (EU) 2019/1111 of 25 June 2019 on jurisdiction, the recognition and enforcement of decisions in matrimonial matters and the matters of parental responsibility, and on international child abduction (recast), *ST/8214/2019/INIT*, *OJ L* 178, 2.7.2019.

Council Regulation (EC) No 4/2009 of 18 December 2008 on jurisdiction, applicable law, recognition and enforcement of decisions and cooperation in matters relating to maintenance obligations, *OJ L* 7, 10.1.2009.

Procedure 2023/0027/CNS, COM (2023) 64: Proposal for a COUNCIL DECISION on an authorisation addressed to France to negotiate a bilateral agreement with Algeria on matters related to judicial cooperation concerning family law matters (Adopted act: 32024D0592).

Proposal for a Council Decision on an authorisation addressed to France to negotiate a bilateral agreement with Algeria on matters related to judicial cooperation concerning family law matters, Brussels, 8.2.2023 COM (2023) 64 final 2023/0027 (CNS),

Act on Resolving Conflict of Laws with the Regulations of other Countries, *Official Gazette of the SFRY*, 43/82 and 72/82 - corr., *Official Gazette of the FRY*, 46/96 and *Official Gazette of the of the RS*, 46/2006.

Family Act, *Official Gazette of the RS*, 18/2005, 72/2011, 6/215.

Agreement between the Republic of Serbia and the Republic of Turkey on mutual legal assistance in civil and commercial matters dated June 5, 2013, *Official Gazette of the RS - International Agreements*, No. 15/2015.

EU Charter (Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, *OJ C* 326, 26 October 2012).

Internet Sources

Study Group of the International Law Commission, *Fragmentation of International Law: difficulties arising from the diversification and expansion of International Law*, Document A/CN.4/L.682 and Add.1, finalized by Mr. Martti Koskeniemi, 13 April 2006, pp. 268-271, available at: https://legal.un.org/ilc/documentation/english/a_cn4_l682.pdf.

Documents

Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties, 22 May 1969, 1155 UNTS 331.

ICJ, Ahmadou Sadio Diallo (Republic Guinea v. Democratic Republic Congo) (compensation owed by the Democratic Republic of the Congo to the Republic of Guinea), Judgment, 2012, ICJ Rep. 324 (June 19, 2012), Declaration of Judge Greenwood.

Koskenniemi, M., The ILC Report, Study on the Function and Scope of the Lex Specialis rule and the Question of 'Self-Contained Regimes', 4 ILC, 7 May 2004, ILC(LVI)SG/ FIL/CRD.1

European Commission, Proposal for a Council Decision on an authorisation addressed to France to negotiate a bilateral agreement with Algeria on matters related to judicial cooperation concerning family law matters, Brussels, 8.2.2023 COM (2023) 64 final 2023/0027 (CNS).